

Research Article

Ventilator Associated Pneumonia and Its Impacts on Prognosis

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ABSTRACT

Objective: Our research was aimed at the evaluation of the ventilator-associated pneumonia (VAP) spectrum and length relation of the stay at the ICU, patient's gender and age were the reasons of discharge from the Intensive Care Unit (ICU).

Study Design: Cross-sectional Research

Place and Duration of Study: Research was completed in the time span of one year from April, 2015 to April, 2016 at the venue of Shifa International Hospital, Islamabad.

Material and Methods: Research sample consisted of a total of 470 cases and out of the total sample 106 cases were diagnosed VAP and they spent more than 48 hours in ICU on mechanical ventilator. They presented positive tracheo-bronchial secretions culture including one of these; more than 48 – hours chest radiograph infiltrate, fever above 38.3°C, leukocytosis above $12 \times 10^9/\text{ml}$ and elevation in the tracheo-bronchial secretions which established VAP diagnosis.

Results: Male and female had the mean age factor respectively 49.8 ± 18 and 50.6 ± 21.4 years with an average ICU stay of 16.6 ± 13 days. Acinetobacterbaumanni was observed in 30.2% VAP patients having colistin sensitivity of 96.8%, 27.4% cases presented Klebsiella pneumonia with the sensitivity rate of 72 and 62 percent respectively in colistin and carbapenems. Methicillin-resistant Staphylococcus aureus was observed in 15.1% patients having a rate of 100% vancomycin sensitivity. An increase of VAP late-onset incidence of 60.4% was contrasted with 39.6% in respect of an early VAP onset. VAP cases presented a 28.6% rate of mortality.

Conclusion: Our research recommends colistin therapy combined with vancomycin and carbapenems in the cases of VAP. There was no significant statistical association in the ICU stay length and the rate of overall mortality of the patients. Discharge odds were 3.2 times of male cases were more than the female cases. A decrease in the factor of age was linked to the discharge factor from ICU.

Keywords: Intensive Care Unit (ICU), Mortality and Ventilator associated pneumonia.

INTRODUCTION

Patients had a significant concern about the VAP during ICU stay on mechanical ventilation. Twenty-seven percent of the patients were significantly critical by the second common most infection in ICU. Every patient developed VAP in the forty-eight hours of mechanical ventilation that ranged from 6 – 52 percent, which can further reach up to 76%. In the development of this

pneumonia the hospital stay increase from 7 – 9 days. VAP risk is high in the early days of mechanical ventilation as 3%/day in next 5 – 10 days 2% and next every day 1%. Mortality rate is documented as 0 – 50 percent in VAP cases.

Mortality results of various research studies are different because of various differences of empirical medical therapy in the time of first two

days, documentation, radiographic examination other than micro-biological and assessment of secretions of respiration [1, 2, 3]. The analysis of the VAP factors and microbiological VAP cases primarily affected mortality rate by ARDS were not included in the research. Mechanical ventilation starting date, mechanical ventilation and airway form identification, i.e. tracheostomy or tracheal, were documented [4, 5, 6, 7]. Every patient was observed for setting and ventilator mode or any other change regularly. Aeruginosa tracheobronchial secretions and *Acinetobacter baumannii* presented a positive culture including any *Stenotrophomonas maltophilia*. One of these clinical investigation such as >48 hours' chest suspicion infiltrate for VAP diagnosis in radiograph, fever (>38.3°C) and leukocytosis in critical cases. It is recommended that prevention requires respiratory intervention therapies. Our VAP knowledge developed significance about pathogenesis, diagnostic testing, risk factors, prevention and therapies by risk factor modification [8, 9].

MATERIAL AND METHODS

We employed a consecutive non-probability technique of sampling for data collection and included 95 cases in the research by using WHO calculator keeping; Confidence level (95%) and required absolute precision (1%). Only 106 cases were diagnosed for VAP for male and female above fifteen years old. VAP was presented in cases who were having pneumonia as they got admission or diagnosed in first 48 hours with respiratory distress (>12 × 10⁹/ml) and tracheo-

bronchial secretions. Routine observation was made about the patient's physical examination, position and oxygen saturation. Sedation of the patients were carried out in primary ventilation including blood culture, urine and tracheal tube investigation as required. Sputum collection was made through suction catheter tip and shifted through sterile tube. VAP diagnosis was made through clinical grounds on the basis of modified (CPIS) that gave 0–2 points each for fever, leukocyte count, radiographic abnormality type, purulence, quantity, oxygenation status and tracheal secretions including sputum culture and gram stain outcomes (Table-I). Analysis of sensitivity and culture was also documented for every antibiotics organism. After the establishment of VAP association initiation of antibiotic therapy was made. To correct abnormality regular analysis of 12-hour Arterial Blood Gases (ABGs) was carried out, to ascertain ICU stay effect Binary Logistic Regression was carried out, in negative and controlled cultures gender and age was also observed, under treatment cases were rejected in logistic regression (p-value <0.05).

RESULTS

470/600 cases agreed for the participation in research and VAP was diagnosed in 106 cases during mechanical ventilation in ICU. Chest X-Ray infiltrates were observed in (71.6%) 76/106 cases. VAP was developed in 42 (39.6%) and 64 (60.4%) patients respectively in first 4 and after 4 days.

Table-I: Clinical pulmonary infection scoring system

CPIS* points	0	1	2
Tracheal secretions	Rare	Abundant	Purulent
Leukocyte count (mm ³)	>4,000 and <11,000	<4,000 and >11,000	<4,000 or >11,000 + band forms
Temperature (°C)	>36.5 and <38.4	>38.5 and <38.9	> 39 or <36
PaO ₂ /FiO ₂ ratio (mmHg)	<240 or ARDS**	-	≤ 240 and no ARDS
Chest radiograph	No infiltrate	Diffuse infiltrate	Localized infiltrate
Culture of tracheal aspirate	Negative	-	Positive
*Clinical pulmonary infection scoring system (CPIS)		**Acute respiratory distress syndrome (ARDS)	

Table-II: Common clinic pathologic features in patients with ventilator associated pneumonia

Variables	Yes (N=106)	
	Number	Percentage
Fever	81	76.4
Leukocytosis	82	77.3
Purulent secretions	104	98.1
Chest X ray Infiltrates	76	71.6

Table-III: Distribution of bacterial isolates from patients diagnosed with ventilator associated pneumonia

Organisms	N = 160	
	Freq	Percentage
Acinetobacterbaumanni	32	30.2
Klebsiellapneumoniae	29	27.4
MRSA*	16	15.1
Pseudomonas aeruginosa	10	9.4
Escherichia coli	8	7.5
Stenotrophomonasmaltophilia	4	3.8
Serratiamarscescens	3	2.8
Proteus	2	1.9
Burkholderiacepacia	1	0.9
VRE**	1	0.9

*Methicillin resistant Staphylococcus aureus (MRSA)
**Vancomycin resistant enterococci (VRE)

Mean age (49.86 ± 18.03) and (50.60 ± 21.49) years was observed in male and female cases respectively. Respective ratio of male and female was 64 (60.4%) and 42 (39.6%). Symptoms were reflected in VAP cases (30.2%) having *Acinetobacter baumannii* (96.8%) colistin sensitivity, 27.4% with *Klebsiella pneumoniae* having 72% & 62% sensitivity respectively colistin & carbapenems and 15.1% presented methicillin resistant *Staphylococcus aureus* having linezolid and vancomycin 100% sensitivity (Table-IV). An increase was observed in late and early VAP onset respectively 60.4% and 39.6% with a mortality rate of 28.6% (Table-III). Multi-drug resistance (MDR), extensive drug resistance (XDR) and pan-drug resistance (PDR) was observed in *Klebsiella*, *E-coli* and pneumonia, colistin sensitivity *Acinetobacter baumannii* respectively.

DISCUSSION

Most repeated infection acquired in hospital-stay was VAP with an increased rate of mortality and cost. Endotracheal tube placement is linked with VAP occurrence. Left over 22 out of 106 (20.8%) cases are still under observation. ICU stay length, gender and age of patients for the VAP prevention was analysed through binary regression. to prevent the ventilator associated pneumonia. VAP was documented in 106 out of 470 patients. According to Nagelkerke model 16.8 percent variance was correctly classified in 73.8 percent patients. There was no statistical significance in mortality rate and hospital stay with a significant p-value (≥ 0.05). Greater odds were observed in males in comparison to females as 3.2 time higher (p-value=0.02). An association was present in less age and hospital discharge (p-value=0.04).

Table-IV: VAP associated organisms and their sensitivity to antibiotics

Antibiotics	<i>Acinetobacter baumannii</i> (N = 32)		<i>Klebsiella pneumoniae</i> (N = 29)		MRSA* (N = 16)		<i>Pseudomonas aeruginosa</i> (N = 10)		<i>E-coli</i> ** (N = 8)		<i>Stentrophomonas</i> (N= 4)		<i>Proteus</i> (N = 2)	
	Number	Percentage	Number	Percentage	Number	Percentage	Number	Percentage	Number	Percentage	Number	Percentage	Number	Percentage
Amikacin	1	3	17	58.6	0	0	6	60	8	100	0	0	2	100
Ceftazidime	0	0	0	0	0	0	5	50	0	0	1	25	1	50
Ciprofloxacin	0	0	8	27	0	0	3	30	1	12.5	3	75	2	100
Imipenem	0	0	18	62	0	0	3	30	7	87.5	0	0	2	100
Piperacillin	0	0	14	48.2	0	0	4	40	5	62.5	2	50	2	100
Meropenem	0	0	18	62	0	0	2	20	7	87.5	0	0	2	100
Levofloxacin	0	0	2	6	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Ceftriaxone	1	3	1	3	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Cefoperazone /Sulbactam	2	6	14	48.2	0	0	3	30	5	62.5	2	50	2	100
Colistin	31	96.8	21	72.4	0	0	8	80	3	37.5	0	0	0	0
Septtran DS	5	15.6	5	17.2	11	68.7	0	0	1	12.5	3	75	1	50
Linezolid	0	0	0	0	16	100	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Vancomycin	0	0	0	0	16	100	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0

*Methicillin resistant *staphylococcus aureus* (MRSA), ***Escherichia coli*

Matching results were presented by Goliain terms of hospital mechanical ventilation of four or above four days as 44.23% and 55.77% patients presented an early and late onset of 4 and above 4 days respectively. In comparison to the research of Kumar mortality (44%) rate was noted as 28.6%. According to Gadani incidence of organism Pseudomonas and Klebsiella was 43.2% & 18.91 percent respectively that followed E. coli, Methicillin resistant Staphylococcus aureus (MRSA), Streptococcus pneumonia and Acinetobacter. Our study observed Acinetobacter, Klebsiella, Pseudomonas and E-coli respectively 30.2%, 27.4%, 15.1%, 9.1% and 7.5%.

Multidrug resistance (MDR), extensive drug resistance (XDR) and pan-drug resistance (PDR) were respectively resistant to one in three, one in two and all antibacterial categories. Our research found MDR, XDR and PDR respectively in E-coli

and Klebsiella, Acinetobacter having colistin sensitivity and only Acinetobacter (Table-IV).

Although VAP responsible organisms are able for the spread of the pleural space or blood in <10% cases in the presence of VAP culture in suspected pneumonia, which requires certain treatment. Therefore, VAP evaluation includes 2 blood cultures and thoracentesis for non-loculated pleural effusions of (≥ 10 mm) diameter and lateral chest decubitus X-ray. USG guidance is required for loculated effusion. Blood sensitivity was observed <25% for VAP diagnosis when the positive culture is present and 64% cases may get this infection from an extra pulmonary infection. Due to low sensitivity we did not include the VAP criteria, if the administration is delayed mortality increases in VAP. It was observed in our research that Acinetobacter with 96.8% colistin sensitivity was present in 30.2% cases, respectively colistin and carbapennems 72 – 62 percent sensitivity was

observed in 27.4% Klebsiella patients and to colistin and 100% linezolid and vancomycin sensitivity was observed in 15.1% methicillin resistant Staphylococcus aureus patients. Monitoring of renal function including vancomycin therapy and colistin increases the chances of renal failure. Controlled management of the therapy for multidrug resistant carbapenemase—which produces K. pneumonia, P. aeruginosa or extensive drug-resistant A. baumannii need to be managed in ICU. According to Caceres and colleague's females has no association with worst clinical outcomes in comparison to males in ICU for VAP. Greater odds were observed in males in comparison to females as 3.2 time higher (p-value = 0.02). An association was present in less age and hospital discharge (p-value = 0.04).

CONCLUSION

Our research recommends colistin therapy combined with vancomycin and carbapenem in the cases of VAP. There was no significant statistical association in the ICU stay length and the rate of overall mortality of the patients. Discharge odds were 3.2 times of male cases were more than the female cases. A decrease in the factor of age was linked to the discharge factor from ICU.

REFERENCES

1. Adkins, B. (2017). Ventilator-Associated Pneumonia.
2. Gutiérrez-Pizarra, A., Amaya-Villar, R., & Garnacho-Montero, J. (2017). Nebulized colistin in ventilator-associated pneumonia: Should we trust it?. *Journal of critical care*, *41*, 328-329.
3. Kalil, A. C., Metersky, M., & Klompas, M. (2017). Management of Adults With Hospital-acquired and Ventilator-associated Pneumonia: 2016 Clinical Practice Guidelines by the Infectious Diseases Society of America and the American Thoracic Society (vol 63, pg e61, 2016). *CLINICAL INFECTIOUS DISEASES*, *65*(8), 1431-1435.
4. Kalil, A. C., Metersky, M., & Klompas, M. (2017). Executive Summary: Management of Adults With Hospital-acquired and Ventilator-associated Pneumonia: 2016 Clinical Practice Guidelines by the Infectious Diseases Society of America and the American Thoracic Society (vol 63, pg 575, 2016). *CLINICAL INFECTIOUS DISEASES*, *65*(7), 1251-1251.
5. Kollef, M. H., Ricard, J. D., Roux, D., Francois, B., Ischaki, E., Rozgonyi, Z., ... & Koura, F. (2017). A randomized trial of the amikacin fosfomycin inhalation system for the adjunctive therapy of Gram-negative ventilator-associated pneumonia: IASIS Trial. *Chest*, *151*(6), 1239-1246.
6. Brotfain, E., Borer, A., Koyfman, L., Saidel-Odes, L., Frenkel, A., Gruenbaum, S. E., ... & Klein, M. (2017). Multidrug resistance acinetobacter bacteremia secondary to ventilator-associated pneumonia: risk factors and outcome. *Journal of intensive care medicine*, *32*(9), 528-534.
7. Lawal, O., Muhamadali, H., Ahmed, W. M., White, I. R., Nijsen, T. M., Goodacre, R., & Fowler, S. J. (2018). Headspace volatile organic compounds from bacteria implicated in ventilator-associated pneumonia analysed by TD-GC/MS. *Journal of breath research*, *12*(2), 026002.
8. Feeney, M., Lindsey, D., Vazquez, D., Porter, K., & Murphy, C. (2018). 688: Identifying Risk Factors For Mrsa Pneumonia In Sicu Patients With Ventilator-associated Pneumonia. *Critical Care Medicine*, *46*(1), 330.
9. Drusano, G. L., Corrado, M. L., Girardi, G., Ellis-Grosse, E. J., Wunderink, R. G., Donnelly, H., ... & Ferrari, M. (2018). Dilution Factor of Quantitative Bacterial Cultures Obtained by Bronchoalveolar Lavage in Patients with Ventilator-Associated Bacterial Pneumonia. *Antimicrobial agents and chemotherapy*, *62*(1), e01323-17.